

A multicolor bioluminescent toolbox for multiplex glow-in-the-dark nucleic acid diagnostics

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Teaser: Multicolor bioluminescent sensors detect two pathogens in one test, enabling rapid diagnostics in low-resource settings.

Abstract: Combining bioluminescent sensors and isothermal amplification enables fast and simple nucleic acid diagnostics, holding great potential for point-of-care applications. We previously developed the LUNAS (LUminescent Nucleic Acid Sensor) platform, which integrates Recombinase Polymerase Amplification (RPA) with a CRISPR dCas9-mediated bioluminescent readout. Here, we extend LUNAS into a multiplex platform through the development of green- and red-light emitting LUNAS variants. These color variants can be integrated with duplex RPA for amplification and orthogonal detection of two DNA targets in a single reaction, without compromising sensitivity or reaction speed. Using this approach, we developed a duplex assay for the sexually transmitted infections gonorrhea and chlamydia, with attomolar sensitivity and a robust ratiometric readout. Using a simple digital camera, multicolor LUNAS enabled detection of bacterial DNA from clinical samples with loads down to ~ 100 copies/ μL and within ~ 30 min, demonstrating its diagnostic performance for low-resource applications.

Introduction

The ability to exponentially amplify nucleic acids and detect them sequence specifically makes them favorable analytes for diagnosing infectious diseases. Quantitative PCR (qPCR) is the molecular diagnostics method of choice for detecting a pathogen's DNA/RNA fingerprint in the laboratory, but is not suitable for an out-of-the-lab application due to the need for advanced equipment and operating personnel. In recent years, various nucleic acid detection methods have been developed that are more amenable to point-of-need use, typically based on isothermal nucleic acid amplification technologies (iNAATs) such as loop-mediated amplification (LAMP) and recombinase polymerase amplification (RPA)¹⁻³. Unlike qPCR, these iNAATs do not require expensive thermal cycling equipment and rapidly amplify target nucleic acids to detectable levels in a continuous manner at a constant temperature. Both nonspecific and sequence-specific methods have been developed to detect the resulting amplicons. The most prominent subcategory of the latter are CRISPR-based diagnostics (CRISPR Dx), predominantly based on collateral cleavage activity by type V (Cas12) or VI (Cas13) effector nucleases⁴⁻⁸. With specificity down to a single base pair, CRISPR Dx methods mitigate the spurious amplification that typically limits iNAATs specificity⁹.

Differentiation between multiple nucleic acid sequences in a single test can be useful in cases of infectious disease where multiple causative agents fit the clinical presentation of a patient or to incorporate an internal positive control target^{10,11}. Such multiplexing can be achieved by splitting up a single sample and distributing it over multiple parallel detection reactions each programmed for detection of a specific sequence. Although straightforward in terms of assay design and highly scalable, this spatial multiplexing approach requires additional sample handling steps or a sophisticated microfluidic device for sample distribution and may cause sample exhaustion¹²⁻¹⁶. Multiplexing within a single test reaction, on the other hand, puts the challenge at the molecular level, necessitating a different reporter signal for each target. Similar to multiplex qPCR using different fluorophore-quencher probes for different sequences, multiplex CRISPR Dx assays have been developed employing different fluorophore-quencher reporters for fluorescent readout, or using a lateral flow assay (LFA) set-up that distinguishes between different reporters^{17,18}. By combining DNA-cleaving Cas12 with RNA-cleaving Cas13 and/or using Cas13 homologs with orthogonal trans-cleavage preferences, up to 4 different target nucleic acids have been differentiated in a single reaction¹⁷. However, few studies have reported successful combination of preamplification through multiplex RPA with multiplex Cas12/Cas13 amplicon detection in a one-pot reaction, and mostly with reduced sensitivity^{19,20}. Moreover, a fluorescence reader with multiple excitation and emission filters is needed for readout, which makes implementation in low-resource settings a challenge. While the LFA-based readout offers an equipment-free alternative, this method is prone to cross-contamination due to post-amplification reaction transfer to the LFA dipstick, resulting in false positives.

We recently developed a one-pot bioluminescent CRISPR diagnostic method, LUNAS, based on RPA and dCas9-mediated split-NanoLuc luciferase reconstitution (Figure 1A)²¹. In this method, two *S. pyogenes* dCas9 (SpdCas9) proteins, one fused to the main luciferase fragment (LargeBiT) and the

other to the complementary activating peptide (SmallBiT), are complexed with gRNAs targeting neighboring sequences in a target DNA, resulting in luciferase reconstitution and a blue bioluminescent signal upon target binding. The inclusion of a green calibrator luciferase enables robust ratiometric detection, with a clear green to blue color shift for a positive test. A key advantage of LUNAS compared to alternative CRISPR Dx methods is the fact that the bioluminescent signal can be readout by a simple camera, making it especially suited for point-of-need use. The original LUNAS method does not allow for spectral multiplexing however, with only a blue luminescent sensor complex available.

In this work, we report the development of orthogonal green and red LUNAS color variants, using bioluminescence resonance energy transfer (BRET) to shift the luminescent color of split-NanoLuc (Figure 1B)²². We show that the two LUNAS color variants can be combined with a complementary calibrator of a third color to develop one-pot duplex RPA-LUNAS assay to detect and discriminate between two common sexually transmitted infection (STI) causing bacteria *N. gonorrhoea* and *C. trachomatis* DNA (Figure 1C). Finally, we demonstrate the rapid and sensitive detection of these STIs in patient samples using a simple digital camera for readout, showcasing the method's promise for low-resource settings.

Fig 1: Schematic overview of multicolor LUNAS for identifying two different targets. (A) Overview of the LUNAS platform. Target DNA is amplified using RPA and detected using two dCas9 proteins fused to split luciferase fragments ('LUNAS proteins') that bind to neighboring sites in target DNA to reconstitute a full luciferase, resulting in blue-light luminescence. Components are combined in a one-pot reaction and readout using a digital camera, also including a green-light emitting luciferase for signal calibration. (B) Development of orthogonal green and red LUNAS color variants, and a red calibrator luciferase. (C) LUNAS color variants allow multiplexed nucleic acid detection. In a one-pot reaction, two targets are co-amplified through duplex RPA and detected using two different LUNAS color variants (green, middle; and blue, right). A third color calibrator is added for signal calibration (red, left).

Results

Development of green LUNAS

In the original LUNAS method, a green light emitting calibrator luciferase is included in the one-pot RPA-LUNAS reaction mixture to achieve a robust ratiometric readout, correcting for substrate depletion and sample matrix effects²¹. This integrated calibration strategy, initially developed in our group for use in the bioluminescent immunodiagnostic method RAPPID, employs a tight fusion of the bright green fluorescent protein mNeonGreen (mNG) to NanoLuc (NL) luciferase, designed by Suzuki et al.^{22,23}. The mNG-NL construct shows efficient BRET, leading to a green-shifted luminescence emission spectrum ($\lambda_{\max} \sim 520$ nm) that can be clearly distinguished from the natural blue (split) NanoLuc emission ($\lambda_{\max} \sim 460$ nm). Based on this construct, a green version of the RAPPID sensor was successfully developed previously by fusion of mNG N-terminally to the SBIT component of split NanoLuc, enabling duplex detection of two different cell surface cancer biomarkers²⁴.

To develop a green version of LUNAS, we screened multiple fusions of mNG and split NanoLuc components of the LUNAS proteins for efficient BRET, which is crucial to limit crosstalk between the blue and green sensors when combined in a duplex assay. The fluorescent proteins were tightly fused to the SBIT or LBIT on either the N- or C-terminal end, resulting in 4 different variants and 8 potential green LUNAS pair combinations (4 single mNG and 4 double mNG LUNAS pairs). Following successful expression of all proteins (Figure S1), the sensor functionality and BRET efficiency of the different pairs were tested using a previously developed LUNAS assay detecting a synthetic SARS-CoV-2 cDNA target fragment (Figure 2A)²¹. All combinations proved functional, showing a clear increase in green luminescence intensity over background level when 500 pM target DNA was present, with green/blue (533/458 nm) emission ratios ranging from 1.0 (dCas9-LBIT-mNG x dCas9-SBIT) to 24 for the combination of dCas9-mNG-LBIT and dCas9-SBIT-mNG (Figure 2A, 2B, S2). Comparing LBIT sensor constructs, most efficient BRET was achieved by fusing mNeonGreen to the N-terminal end of the luciferase fragment for all SBIT partner combinations, whereas for SBIT constructs the best performer depends on the complexation partner. The most optimal pair (dCas9-mNG-LBIT x dCas9-SBIT-mNG), which we refer to as 'green LUNAS', was tested in a previously developed one-pot RPA-LUNAS assay to detect a synthetic SARS-CoV-2 cDNA target (Figure 2C). Addition of target DNA resulted in a clear increase in green-light luminescence (Figure 2D, right), similar to the increase in blue-light luminescence when using the original blue LUNAS (Figure 2D, left), proving that green LUNAS is compatible with one-pot RPA reaction conditions²¹. While the signal of the green LUNAS shows minimal residual luminescence in the blue channel (~7%), the higher degree of bleed-through of the blue LUNAS signal into the green channel (~15%) in combination with its higher peak signal level in this assay does result in prominent green light emission by the blue LUNAS. To correct for this bleed-through, we applied a spectral unmixing correction based on the emission spectra of the LUNAS variants by subtracting a corresponding fraction of the luminescence intensity at peak wavelength from the level at the secondary color channel, which effectively resolves the cross-talk (Figure 2D, S3).

Figure 2: Green LUNAS development. (A) Schematic overview and green-over-blue ratios of the different mNeonGreen LUNAS fusions. dCas9-LBiT (L) and dCas9-SBiT (S) are fused to mNeonGreen (g, N-terminal and C-terminal) and can be combined to obtain a green LUNAS (left). Green-over-blue ratios for the different combinations (right). LUNAS proteins were used at a concentration of 1 nM (LB variants); 10 nM (SB variants), complexed with gRNAs targeting SARS-CoV-2 ORF1a target. Target cDNA was added to a final concentration of 500 pM. Bars represent average values and circles represent individual measurements (n = 3). (B) Emission spectra of original blue LUNAS (blue) and dCas9-mNG-LBiT x dCas9-SBiT-mNG (green). Measurements were performed using 1 nM LUNAS-LB:gRNA_SC2ORF1a_B and 10 nM LUNAS-SB:gRNA_SC2ORF1a_A RNP variants, and 500 pM SARS-CoV-2 cDNA target. Spectra are normalized to peak emission wavelengths. (C) Schematic overview of one-pot RPA-LUNAS assay using either blue or green LUNAS. (D) Blue and green luminescence of a one-pot RPA-LUNAS assay for SARS-CoV-2 cDNA using either blue LUNAS or green LUNAS. Assays were performed with 1000 copies of synthetic target DNA input, using 1 nM SpdCas9-LB:gRNA_ORF1a_B; 10 nM SpdCas9-SB:gRNA_ORF1a_A or 1 nM SpdCas9-mNG-LB:gRNA_ORF1a_B; 10 nM SpdCas9-SB-mNG:gRNA_ORF1a_A in a 20 μ L reaction. Individual replicate traces (n = 2) are shown, with a bleed-through correction (blue = blue - 0.04 * green, green = green - 0.15 * blue) and smoothing filter (rolling average, 7-point centered) applied.

Development of red calibrator luciferase and red LUNAS

To distinguish two targets using different color channels and still apply the internal calibration method, use of a third color channel is required. To complete a tri-color LUNAS toolbox and allow for interchangeable use of different LUNAS and calibrator luciferase combinations in a duplex assay, we set out to develop both a red-light emitting LUNAS variant and calibrator luciferase. The development of luciferases emitting at the red end of the visible light spectrum is also highly desired for imaging and sensing applications in tissue and blood, matrices that strongly absorb light of wavelengths below 600 nm²⁵. Red-shifting the blue luminescence spectrum of NanoLuc beyond the green range using BRET is challenging, as strong spectral overlap between donor and acceptor is essential for efficient resonance energy transfer. Fusions or insertions of orange/red fluorescent proteins (in)to NanoLuc have been reported, but show limited BRET efficiency, resulting in considerable residual emission in the blue wavelength range^{22,25,26}. As an alternative, the conjugation of organic fluorophores to NanoLuc to generate color variants has been reported by various groups, but also these generally show limited BRET efficiency in the case of orange/red variants²⁷⁻²⁹. As a notable exception, Winssinger's group recently reported a red-shifted NanoLuc variant with an impressive 674/450 nm emission ratio of 14.5, but this

requires use of a synthetic high affinity SBIT variant and still uses fluorophores with suboptimal overlap with NanoLuc emission³⁰.

We therefore opted to use the large Stokes shift ATTO490LS dye ($\lambda_{\text{ex,max}} \sim 496$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{em,max}} \sim 661$ nm), coupling it to various positions within NanoLuc using specific thiol-maleimide labeling. Large Stokes shift organic fluorophores and fluorescent proteins emit photons that are spectrally well separated from their optimal excitation light as a result of (a combination of) photophysical and/or photochemical effects such as internal charge transfer (ICT) and excited state proton transfer (ESPT)³¹⁻³³. Compared to commonly used red dyes like Cy3 and ATTO647N, the ATTO490LS dye features an excitation spectrum that overlaps more extensively with NanoLuc emission, which could render it a good red light emitting BRET acceptor.

To efficiently screen for suitable BRET positions within NanoLuc, a red calibrator luciferase was developed first. A short distance between donor and acceptor is key to efficient BRET and hence, residues in loop regions in close proximity to the active site (T41, G66, S68, G113, G136, G159) were selected for dye coupling, presuming these residues could be mutated without drastically impacting protein folding and catalytic function. Additionally, position D148 located in a loop region on the opposite side of the beta barrel compared to the other selected residues was included in the screening, as it was previously used successfully in our group to create a BRET-based NanoLuc – thiazole orange luminescent intercalating dye conjugate (LUMID)⁴. The selected positions were individually mutated to cysteines and the native Cys166 present in NanoLuc was mutated to a serine (NL_C166S = NL*), which is known not to impact luciferase activity³⁴. Following successful expression and purification (with the exception of NL*_G113C, showing clear impurities, see Figure S4), the luminescence intensities of the cysteine mutants were compared to that of wildtype NanoLuc. Most mutants showed a modest 2 to 3-fold decrease in emission intensity, except for the D148C variant, which maintained wildtype intensity (Figure S5A). Subsequent labelling of the proteins was confirmed to be (nearly) complete by absorbance measurement and mass spectrometry (Figure S6). All of the resulting dye conjugates showed red luminescence, with red/blue (653/458 nm) emission ratios ranging from 0.6 (NL*_D148C-ATTO490LS) to 9.1 (NL*_T41C-ATTO490LS). The red (653 nm) emission intensities were lower than wildtype NanoLuc blue emission intensity (3 – 34% of blue intensity, Figure 3A, S5B), which can be ascribed to the relatively low fluorescence quantum yield of ATTO490LS ($\eta_{\text{fl}} = 0.3$). The NL*_T41C-ATTO490LS variant was considered most optimal, having the highest BRET ratio and adequate emission intensity. To better conform with the enzymatic kinetics of the split luciferase used in the LUNAS sensor³⁵, a version of the red calibrator based on fused SBIT and LBIT was developed using the same T41C labelling site (NB_T41C-ATTO490LS), resulting in a similar red/blue (653/458 nm) ratio of 8.9 (Figure 3B, S7, S8, S9).

The red split calibrator design was used as a starting point for developing a red LUNAS variant. For both the LBIT and SBIT sensor parts, two residues were individually mutated to cysteines, whilst the two native SpCas9 cysteines were mutated to serines (C80S, C574S, which are known to have little impact on its functioning³⁶). For the LBIT sensor part, the most-efficient BRET positions from the calibrator screening were tested (T41 and G66). For the SBIT sensor part, positions N-terminal (K-4, meaning the lysine in the linker 4 residues N-terminal of SBIT) and C-terminal (K+2, meaning the lysine in the linker 2 residues C-terminal of SBIT) of SBIT were tested, not to interfere with luciferase reconstitution. The resulting 4 successfully expressed, purified (Figure S10) and labelled (ATTO490LS-maleimide, degree

of labelling > 0.9) proteins were combined with each other or the classic blue LUNAS proteins, screening a total of 8 candidate red LUNAS pairs. The red/blue (653/458 nm) emission ratios observed show a clear benefit of labelling both the dCas9-SBiT and the dCas9-LBiT proteins, with single dye LUNAS pairs featuring red/blue emission ratios of 1.7 – 2.9, versus 8.1 – 13.2 for double labelled pairs (Figure 3C, S11).

Next, the LUNAS pair with the highest BRET efficiency, combining dCas9*-LBiT_T41C-ATTO490LS (L41R) with dCas9*-SBiT_K-4C-ATTO490LS (S-4R), termed 'red LUNAS' (Figure 3D), was used in a duplex one-pot RPA-LUNAS assay. For this, RPA primers and gRNAs were designed to detect the human Ribonuclease P protein subunit p30 mRNA ((Hs)RPP30), which is commonly used as a positive control target in multiplex molecular diagnostics tests for human sample material to confirm correct sample preparation^{37,38}. This RPP30 assay was combined with the previously reported SARS-CoV-2 (ORF1a target) RPA-LUNAS assay, programming the green LUNAS to detect RPP30 and the red LUNAS for SARS-CoV-2 ORF1a detection, and including a blue calibrator (Figure 3E). An initial attempt using equimolar concentrations of both RPP30 and SARS-CoV-2 primer sets showed a negative effect of the presence of the RPP30 primers on the SARS-CoV-2 assay (Figure S13), which may indicate preferential binding of recombinase enzymes to the RPP30 primers. Reducing the amount of RPP30 primers 3-fold (SARS-CoV-2:RPP30 primer ratio = 3:1) to compensate for this effect successfully resolved this issue. Using this primer ratio, the duplex assay showed a clear increase in green/blue ratio in the presence of RPP30 cDNA, whereas the red/blue ratio increased when SARS-CoV-2 ORF1a cDNA was spiked into the reaction, and both the green and red LUNAS were clearly activated when both targets were present (Figure 3F). As the signals of the green and red LUNAS show minimal cross-talk, no unmixing correction was needed in this case (Figure S14). These results illustrate that multicolor RPA-LUNAS can be used to include an internal control reaction detecting a host-specific nucleic acid sequence in addition to pathogen DNA/RNA. Screening of various primer set combinations for designing such duplex RPA-LUNAS will likely contribute to more balanced amplification kinetics and improved assay performance, but was not attempted for this specific assay. Instead, we focused on the development of a novel duplex LUNAS assay to distinguish between related pathogens in a single reaction.

Figure 3: Development of red calibrator and red LUNAS. (A) Left: Schematic overview of NanoLuc structure in complex with azaoelenterazine substrate analog (in cyan) in intra-barrel catalytic site (PDB 8BO9) with mutation and dye conjugation positions highlighted. Right: Red-over-blue ratios (653/458 nm) for different ATTO490LS conjugation positions within NanoLuc, as well as unconjugated native NanoLuc (wt). Bars represent average values and circles represent individual replicates (n = 3). (B) Normalized emission spectra of blue (NB_T41C), green (mNG-NB) and red (NB_T41C-ATTO490LS) split NanoLuc-based calibrator luciferases. Spectra are normalized to peak emission wavelengths. The maximal wavelength range of the platereader was 398-653 nm. (C) Left: Schematic overview of dye conjugation positions in dCas9*-LbIt (L) and dCas9*-SbIt (S) that can be combined to obtain red LUNAS. Right: Red-over-blue ratios (653/458 nm) for different target combinations of ATTO490LS-coupled LUNAS proteins and original LUNAS proteins. LUNAS reactions were performed using 500 pM target DNA (synthetic T7 phage fragment with 50 bp interspace), 10 nM dCas9*-SbIt:gRNA_T7A variant and 1 nM dCas9*-LbIt:gRNA_T7B variant. Bars represent average values and circles represent individual replicates (n = 3). (D) Normalized emission spectra of original blue LUNAS (dCas9-SB x dCas9-LB), green LUNAS (dCas9-SB-mNG x dCas9-mNG-LB) and red LUNAS (dCas9-SB_K-4C-ATTO490LS x dCas9-LB_T41C-ATTO490LS). LUNAS reactions were performed using 500 pM target DNA (SARS-CoV-2 ORF1a), 10 nM LUNAS-SbIt:gRNA_SC2ORF1a_A variant and 1 nM LUNAS-LbIt:gRNA_SC2ORF1a_B variant RNPs. Spectra are normalized to peak emission wavelengths. (E) Schematic overview of the duplex RPA-LUNAS assay using the green LUNAS detecting a human cDNA sequence (HsRPP30), red LUNAS detecting a SARS-CoV-2 cDNA sequence (ORF1a) and split NanoLuc blue calibrator luciferase. (F) One-pot duplex RPA-LUNAS for HsRPP30 (left) and SARS-CoV-2 ORF1a (right) targets. Assays were performed with 1000 cp of synthetic target cDNA input, 160 nM of both RPP30 primers and 480 nM SARS-CoV-2 primers, using 2 nM SpdCas9-mNG-LB:gRNA_RPP30_B; 20 nM SpdCas9-SB-mNG:gRNA_RPP30_A, and 2 nM SpdCas9-LB_T41C-ATTO490LS:gRNA_ORF1a_B; 20 nM SpdCas9-SB_K-4C-ATTO490LS:gRNA_ORF1a_A and 2 pM NB_T41C blue split calibrator in a single 20 μ L reaction. Individual replicate traces (n = 2) are shown, with a rolling average filter (7-point centered) applied to the luminescence readings. NTC: No template control.

Duplex RPA-LUNAS assay for CT/NG

As an initial important application of multicolor LUNAS, we designed a duplex RPA-LUNAS assay for detecting the bacteria *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* (NG) and *Chlamydia trachomatis* (CT), the causative agents of the STIs gonorrhoeae and chlamydia, respectively. Although both can be asymptomatic, CT and NG infections often show overlapping clinical presentations and may also co-occur, warranting a duplex test for simultaneous detection and discrimination of both bacteria³⁹. Given the high prevalence of these diseases that can come with severe complications, the associated stigma that may be a barrier to healthcare seeking, and growing antimicrobial resistance, there is an established need for affordable, fast and reliable point-of-care tests, especially in low-resource settings^{40,41}. To reliably detect both species, we chose to target genes that are highly conserved over their various subtypes: *uvrC* gene for CT and *dcmH* gene for NG (Figure 4A). To establish the assay, we initially designed and screened multiple sets of gRNAs and complementary RPA primers for CT and NG separately, using a single-target blue RPA-LUNAS assay (Figure S15 – S17). Selection criteria included the fold-increase in luminescence intensity and reaction speed. Using the best-performing combinations, down to 20 copies (*uvrC*, CT) and 200 copies (*dcmH*, NG) of synthetic target input could successfully be distinguished from the no template control (NTC) within 20 minutes (Figure 4B). For NG, two out of three replicates with 20 copies (cp) input showed an increase in luminescence; a stochastic assay response characteristic of NAATs at low target concentrations.

Next, the separate CT and NG assays were combined into a duplex assay wherein the blue and green LUNAS target *uvrC* (CT) and *dcmH* (NG), respectively, and the red-light emitting luciferase is used for calibration (Figure 4C). We selected the blue and green LUNAS based on their similar luminescent intensities (Figure S12), though other color combinations could also be used. The duplex assay requires pooling of two primer sets that might interfere with each other, as was observed for the SARS-CoV-2/HsRPP30 assay. Through additional screening for efficient amplification of both target genes as well as for non-specific binding and amplification in the presence of full genomic DNA, we identified an optimal primer combination with *dcmH* primers different from those used in the single-target assays (Figure S18).

To evaluate the performance of the CT/NG duplex RPA-LUNAS, the assay was performed with decreasing concentrations of synthetic target genes. The assay successfully detected as few as 10 copies of target DNA for both CT and NG within 20 min (Figure 4D, S19). Despite the increased number of reaction components (sensor proteins, primers) compared to a single-target RPA-LUNAS, the duplex assay did not compromise on sensitivity or reaction speed. Upon addition of both CT and NG target, the blue- as well as green luminescence increased, also confirming efficient co-amplification and co-detection. For this assay, significant bleed-through was observed for both blue and green LUNAS into the green and blue channel, respectively. Applying a bi-directional bleed-through correction using empirically determined correction factors again successfully minimized this cross-talk, without noticeably affecting blue-over-red (B/R) and green-over-red (G/R) ratio traces of reactions with actual activation of the corresponding LUNAS (Figure 4D, S20). We found that optimal bleed-through correction factors differ per assay due to slight differences in emission spectra, and therefore must be determined separately for each assay.

Fig 4: Development of multicolor RPA-LUNAS assay for CT/NG. (A) Schematic overview of assay target genes for *N. gonorrhoeae* (dcmH gene) and *C. Trachomatis* (uvrC gene). (B) one-pot RPA-LUNAS assay for CT (left) and NG (right) separately, using the blue LUNAS as readout. Assays were performed with 20-20,000 cp of synthetic target DNA input, using 10 nM dCas9-SB:gRNA_CT011/NG008 and 1 nM dCas9-LB:gRNA_CT012/NG004 in a 20 μ L reaction. (C) Schematic overview of the duplex RPA-LUNAS assays using the green LUNAS (NG, dcmH), blue LUNAS (CT, uvrC) and red calibrator. (D) one-pot multiplexed RPA-LUNAS for CT (left) and NG (right). Assays were performed with 10 – 10,000 cp of synthetic target DNA input, using 10 nM blue dCas9-SB:gRNA_CT011, 1 nM blue dCas9-LB:gRNA_CT012, 20 nM green dCas9-SB:gRNA_NG008, 2 nM green dCas9-LB:gRNA_NG004 and 250 pM of red calibrator in a single 20 μ L reaction. Individual replicate traces (single $n = 3$, multiplexed $n = 2$) are shown, with a bleed-through correction (blue = blue - 0.10 * green, green = green - 0.20 * blue) and a rolling average filter (5-point centered) applied to the luminescence readings.

CT/NG duplex assay clinical sample validation

To validate the RPA-LUNAS multiplex assay on clinical samples, we evaluated its performance on a small panel of DNA isolates ($n = 18$) from CT-positive, NG-positive, and CT/NG double-positive patient samples (Figure 5A). The panel included male and female samples with varying pathogen loads and different specimen types, including urine and anal, throat and vaginal swabs (Table S3). All samples were tested in parallel with a commercial qPCR test and a digital droplet PCR (ddPCR) assay to determine target concentration (Figure S21-23). Using a luminescence plate reader as readout, we tested all samples in duplicate, using 1 μ L of DNA isolate in a 20 μ L RPA-LUNAS reaction. Samples were considered positive if the luminescence ratio (B/R or G/R) surpassed a threshold value at timepoint t , determined as the mean luminescence ratio of the no template control (NTC) at that timepoint t plus 8 (blue LUNAS) or 16 (green LUNAS) times the standard deviation of all samples at $t = 5$ minutes. The reported LUNAS threshold time equals the timepoint at which the measured luminescence ratio surpasses this threshold value (Figure 5B, S24). Suitable threshold values were empirically determined for this CT/NG assay, and may be different for other assays, depending on LUNAS signal variation and maximal response.

Using multicolor RPA-LUNAS, all CT- and CT/NG-positive samples (n = 12) were found positive for CT within 25 minutes, with 20/24 duplicates detected in under 15 minutes (Figure 5D). Similarly, all NG-positive samples (n = 6) were detected by our assay within 30 minutes. Most of the double-positive CT/NG samples (n = 6) were also correctly identified positive for NG. However, for one of the samples with a lower target load stochasticity was observed with one out of two replicates showing a signal above the threshold. Interestingly, one CT-positive sample also showed a signal increase in the NG channel (Figure 5D, indicated with *). Subsequent qPCR testing, targeting a different gene (TFPP gene) than the commercial qPCR test, confirmed the presence of NG DNA (C_t value = 27.0), indicating that our assay correctly identified the sample as double-positive, whereas the routine qPCR did not (Figure S25). Importantly, we observed no false positive results using the multicolor RPA-LUNAS assay. Finally, to demonstrate how the combination of isothermal amplification and a multicolor bioluminescent signal make the assay suitable for use in low-resource settings, the assay was also performed using cheap and simple equipment (Figure 5C). The experimental set-up consisted of a 3D-printed light-tight box with a small heating block inside and a standard digital camera on top for signal recording. Half of the sample panel (n = 9) was tested using similar conditions as the plate reader experiment (Figure 5B, D), but using 1 μ L of DNA isolate in a 25 μ L RPA-LUNAS reaction and a 2.5x increased calibrator concentration to allow better visualization. Pictures were captured with a 2-minute shutter time and analyzed using a custom script that automatically identifies wells and computes the mean blue, green and red pixel intensities and corresponding blue-over-red and green-over-red ratios (Figure 5E, F and Supplementary Information). The camera-based set-up produced response curves similar to the plate reader measurements (Figure 5G, S26), successfully identifying all tested samples as positive or negative (Figure 5H). Compared to the plate reader results, the LUNAS threshold times were found to be slightly longer (<30 min for CT-positive, <55 min for NG-positive), likely due to the increased calibrator concentration. These results show that multicolor RPA-LUNAS enables highly sensitive, duplex detection of CT and NG, using a simplified experimental set-up suitable for point-of-care diagnostic applications.

or digital camera, using a light-tight box and heating block. (E) Camera picture processing steps. (F-H) One-pot multiplex RPA-LUNAS for CT-positive, NG-positive and CT/NG double-positive clinical samples, using a digital camera as readout. Tests were performed with 1 μ L of sample input, using 10 nM blue dCas9-SB:gRNA_CT011, 1 nM blue dCas9-LB:gRNA_CT012, 20 nM green dCas9-SB:gRNA_NG008, 2 nM green dCas9-LB:gRNA_NG004 and 625 pM of red calibrator in a single 25 μ L reaction. F) Pictures of a subset of reactions detected using a digital camera, showing the blue/green/red intensity at several points in time. Two consecutive wells shown within the same dashed box represent technical duplicates. (G) Blue/red and green/red ratio traces over time extracted from camera pictures, with a bleed-through correction (blue = blue - 0.10 * green, green = green - 0.20 * blue) and a rolling average filter (5-point centered) applied to the color intensity readings (H) Overview of multiplex RPA-LUNAS outcomes for all samples tested for CT (left) and NG (right), using the digital camera as readout. Circles represent individual data points and duplicates are connected with vertical lines.

Discussion

The multicolor LUNAS platform reported here provides a rapid and sensitive multiplexed nucleic acid detection platform particularly suitable for point-of-care applications. Through tight-fusion of green fluorescent proteins and introducing a large Stokes shift red fluorescent dye close to Nanoluc's active site, green and red LUNAS variants and a red calibrator luciferase were developed, complementary to the original blue LUNAS and green calibrator luciferase. The color variants show highly efficient BRET with BRET ratios > 10, therefore having minimal residual blue luminescence to allow for orthogonal DNA detection in a single reaction. Different LUNAS color variants and calibrator combinations can be mix-and-matched and integrated with a duplex RPA reaction to amplify, detect and distinguish two targets simultaneously. To showcase the platform, we developed a duplex test for the sexually transmitted infections gonorrhoeae and chlamydia with qPCR-like sensitivity and validated its performance using a simple experimental set-up that allows for use in low-resource settings.

The developed 3 colors allow for identification of 2 targets with internal signal calibration (or 3 targets without calibration) in a single reaction. Single reaction multiplexing is highly valuable for infectious disease diagnostics to enable discrimination of different pathogens fitting the patient's clinical presentation in one go, as well as allowing for inclusion of an internal positive control target to check for correct sample collection/processing and assay functioning. Yet, the extent of spectral multiplexing is limited by the amount of orthogonal fluorescent acceptors that can be distinguished in the visual spectrum. For applications requiring the discrimination of more targets, for example in pathogen subtyping, spatial multiplexing through microfluidic distribution of the sample over multiple reaction chambers would be a more straightforward solution. When used in combination, spectral and spatial multiplexing could be synergistic and offer an efficient solution for panel multiplexing.

Other single reaction multiplex CRISPR assays have been reported using a combination of a DNA-cleaving Cas12 enzyme and one or multiple RNA-targeting Cas13 homologs, exploiting their different trans-cleavage sequence preferences for orthogonal fluorescent detection of up to four targets^{17,19,20}. While both LUNAS and these Cas12/Cas13 methods are affected by spectral overlap, Cas12/Cas13 enzymes also exhibit cross-reactivity through secondary ssRNA trans-cleavage by Cas12 enzymes and non-strict sequence preferences of Cas13 collateral activity, resulting in additional cross-talk that can make signal interpretation more difficult^{17,18,42}. Moreover, one-pot integration of multiplex Cas12/Cas13 assays with multiplex RPA is complicated by the many different reaction components involved, including reagents for transcription of dsDNA amplicons to allow detection by Cas13 enzymes^{19,43}. Unlike for LUNAS, successfully integrated one-pot duplex RPA-Cas12/Cas13 assays typically show reduced test sensitivity compared to corresponding single target assays, limiting their use in high-sensitivity applications such as chlamydia/gonorrhoea duplex testing^{19,20}.

Red-shifted luciferase proteins are desirable for biological imaging and sensing, but have historically been difficult to engineer due to limited spectral overlap of red fluorescent acceptors with native blue and yellow luciferases. To our knowledge, our red NanoLuc variant displays the highest BRET efficiency obtained with straightforward thiol-maleimide labelling of the protein, as a result of efficient spectral overlap of the large Stokes shift ATTO490LS dye with NanoLuc and systematic screening of labelling positions. Although Winssinger et al. also reported a red-shifted NanoLuc with impressive BRET efficiencies, this concerns a split system and requires separate addition of a modified high-affinity SBIT peptide, rendering it unsuitable for combination with split NanoLuc-based sensors³⁰. In contrast, the red-shifted NanoLuc developed here could serve as an alternative calibrator luciferase in already-established assays, like in the RAPPID platform, having minimal spectral overlap with native NanoLuc and being compatible with both blue- and green-luminescent sensors²⁴. Furthermore, it may also find purpose in molecular imaging, for example for the development of efficient red bioluminescent antibodies⁴⁴.

The simple LUNAS assay setup, consisting of a cheap and portable device using a digital camera for readout, could enable use at primary healthcare facilities and opens up possibilities for application in low-resource regions, such as in Sub-Saharan Africa. Both *C. trachomatis* and *N. gonorrhoeae* are highly prevalent in these areas, but are mostly treated using a syndromic approach due to limited diagnostic infrastructure⁴⁰. Point-of-care tests could improve accessibility to STI testing to prevent spread and enable early and appropriate treatment, thereby reducing antibiotic misuse and the resulting selection pressure that drives the development of antimicrobial resistance, especially for *N. gonorrhoeae*^{39,45}. To further streamline the platform for such point-of-care applications, next steps will focus on integration of sample pre-processing and the lyophilization of the reaction mixture for increased shelf life.

Methods

Cloning. *Green LUNAS:* pET28a(+) vectors containing LUNAS-LB and LUNAS-SB, and mNG-NanoBiT constructs were already available from previous studies^{21,35}. The N-terminal mNeonGreen fusions were made via traditional restriction/ligation into the pET28a(+) vector by using the pET28a(+)-LUNAS-LBiT/SBiT and the pET-28a(+)-mNG-NanoBiT. The C-terminal fusions were made via Gibson Assembly. The inserts were obtained through PCR (Q5, NEB) on the mNG-NanoBiT vector, using primers containing overhangs overlapping with the LUNAS-LB and LUNAS-SB plasmids to allow incorporation. The NEBuilder HiFi Master Mix was used to perform the Gibson Assembly. Sequences were confirmed using Sanger sequencing (Baseclear).

Red calibrator and Red LUNAS: pET28a(+) vectors containing NanoLuc (Cys-free: C166S), LUNAS-LB and LUNAS-SB constructs were already available from previous studies^{4,21}. To create the LUNAS and NanoLuc cysteine mutants, site-directed mutagenesis to introduce new cysteine residues and mutate native SpdCas9 cysteines to serines (C80S, C574S) was carried out using the QuikChange Lightning Site-Directed Mutagenesis kit (Agilent), using specific primers according to the manufacturer's instructions. The constructs were transformed in either *E. coli* TOP10 cells or XL10-Gold Ultracompetent cells and plated on Lysogeny Broth (LB) agar containing 50 µg/mL kanamycin. Small cultures were prepared using 5 mL LB medium (10 g/L NaCl, 10 g/L Peptone, and 5 g/L yeast extract) supplemented with 50 µg/mL kanamycin, and were grown overnight at 37 °C at 250 rpm. The plasmids were purified using the QIAprep Spin Miniprep Kit according to manufacturer's instructions. Sequences were confirmed using sanger sequencing (Baseclear or Azenta life sciences).

Red split calibrator: A pET28a(+)-mNG-NanoBiT plasmid was available from a previous study³⁵. The mNG sequence was removed using Overhang PCR (NEB Phusion) and subsequent NdeI-HF (NEB) restriction and ligation (NEB T4 DNA ligase), resulting in a pET28a(+)-NanoBiT plasmid. For mutagenesis, introducing T41C, the same method as for the full length NanoLuc based red calibrator was used.

Protein expression and purification. Plasmids encoding calibrator luciferases and LUNAS proteins were transformed into chemically competent *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) and cultured in either LB (10 g Peptone, 10 g NaCl and 5 g yeast extract per liter) (LUNAS proteins and split red calibrator) or 2YT (16 g peptone, 5 g NaCl, 10 g yeast extract per liter) (NL*-based calibrator luciferases) medium supplemented with 50 µg/mL kanamycin. At OD₆₀₀ = 0.6–0.8, protein expression was induced using 0.2 mM (LUNAS proteins) or 1 mM (calibrator luciferases) isopropyl β-D-1-thiogalactopyranoside (IPTG) overnight at 18-20 °C. Subsequently, cells were harvested by centrifugation (10 min, 10,000xg, 4 °C).

For calibrator luciferases, cells were lysed using Bugbuster protein extraction reagent (Novagen), supplemented with Benzonase endonuclease (Novagen) and subsequently centrifuged at 40,000xg for 30 min at 4 °C. For purification, the supernatant was run over a Ni²⁺-NTA affinity column, followed by a washing steps consisting of 1 column volume (CV, 10 mL) of basic buffer (1xPBS, 370 mM NaCl, 20 mM imidazole, 10% (v/v) glycerol, pH 7.4). Proteins were eluted using 1 CV of elution buffer (1xbasic buffer, 230 mM imidazole). Correct protein mass was confirmed by ESI-QToF LC-MS (WatersMassLynx v4.1), using MagTran v1.03 for MS deconvolution. Mass spectra were obtained using a 1 µL injection volume, containing 0.1 mg/mL of protein in ESI-QToF buffer (MilliQ, 0.1% formic acid). Purified proteins were stored in strep elution buffer at -70 °C until further use.

For LUNAS proteins, purification was performed as previously described²¹. Cells were resuspended in 10 mL pre-chilled lysis buffer (500 mM NaCl, 1 mM TCEP, 50 mM Tris pH 8.0) per gram cell pellet, supplemented with Benzonase endonuclease (Novagen) and protease inhibitor cocktail tablet (Merck life science). The cells were lysed by passing them three times through a high-pressure homogenizer (Avestin Emulsiflex C3) at 15,000 – 20,000 Psi and subsequently centrifuged at 40,000xg for 30 min at 4°C. The proteins were purified using Strep-Tactin XT (Iba) purification. Protein purity was confirmed by reducing SDS-PAGE and concentrations were determined by measurement of absorbance at 280 nm on a NanoDrop spectrometer using extinction coefficients calculated from the protein sequence. Proteins in Strep-Tactin XT elution buffer (150 mM NaCl, 100 mM Tris-Cl pH 8.0, 1 mM EDTA, 50 mM D-biotin, 1 mM TCEP) were aliquoted and snap frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -70 °C.

ATTO-maleimide dye conjugation. Proteins were reduced using 5 mM of TCEP for 60 minutes at 500 rpm at RT and subsequently buffer exchanged to 100 mM Sodium Phosphate buffer (pH 7) with 25 µM TCEP using a PD-10 desalting column (G-25, 5000 Da cutoff). Then, the maleimide-ATTO 490LS dye (cat #AD 490LS-41, ATTO-TEC GmbH) was added in a 10-fold molar excess (relative to the amount of cysteines) to 10 µM of reduced protein and allowed to react for 2 hours at room temperature with continuous shaking at 500 rpm. Excess dye was removed using a desalting (PD-10) column (Sephadex G-25, 5000 Da cutoff) equilibrated with 1xPBS (100 mM NaPi, 150 mM NaCl, pH 7.2). SDS-PAGE analysis of purified reactions was performed by imaging the gels with UV to visualize dye and subsequently stain the gels with Bio-Safe Coomassie G-250 Stain to visualize proteins.

For the red LUNAS proteins, 50 kDa MWCO filter (Amicon Ultra 4 mL, Merck) was used to concentrate the protein elutions. The A_{280} and A_{max} absorbance of the elutions were measured using NanoDrop to calculate the protein concentrations and the degree of labeling (DoL) using the following formula: $DoL = A_{max} * \epsilon_{prot} / (A_{280} - A_{max} * CF_{280}) * \epsilon_{max}$. With $CF_{280} = 0.21$, $\epsilon_{prot} = 145890 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for LUNAS-LB and $127440 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for LUNAS-SB, $\epsilon_{max} = 40000 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

For the red (split) calibrator, coupling efficiency and correct mass of the NanoLuc/NanoBiT-ATTO490LS conjugates were confirmed by ESI-QToF LCMS (WatersMassLynx v4.1), using MagTran v1.03 for MS deconvolution. Mass spectra were obtained using a 1 µL injection volume, containing 0.1 mg/mL of protein in Q-ToF buffer (MilliQ, 0.1% formic acid).

Characterization of luminescence spectra and BRET ratios. For the red, green and blue (split) calibrator luciferases, proteins were diluted to 1 nM in 1xPBS buffer supplemented with 1 mg/mL BSA, unless indicated otherwise. 19 µL of protein dilution was combined with 1 µL 50x diluted NanoGlo substrate (Promega) in a Nunc flat-bottom white 384-well microplate. Luminescence spectra (corrected for wavelength-dependent detector sensitivity differences, Tecan internal calibration) were recorded in a plate reader (Tecan Spark 10M) between 398 nm and 653 nm wavelengths with a step size of 15 nm, a bandwidth of 25 nm and an integration time of 150 ms. Green-over-blue and red-over-blue ratios were calculated by dividing luminescence intensity at $533 \pm 12.5 \text{ nm}$ (green) and $653 \pm 12.5 \text{ nm}$ (red) by the intensity at $458 \pm 12.5 \text{ nm}$ (blue), respectively.

For the blue, green and red LUNAS, LUNAS-LB and LUNAS-SB proteins were incubated with 2 – 3x molar excess of gRNA for 15 minutes at 37 °C in LUNAS RNP buffer (20 mM Tris-Cl pH 7.5, 150 mM KCl, 5 mM MgCl_2 , 5% (v/v) glycerol, 1 mM DTT, 1 mg/mL BSA) to form RNP complexes. 2x sensor mixes were prepared by combining LUNAS-LB RNP and LUNAS-SB RNP. 10 µL of sensor mix was combined with 10

μL of target DNA in a white 384 wells flat-bottom plate. The final concentration of LUNAS-LB RNP, LUNAS-SB RNP and target DNA was 1 nM, 10 nM and 500 pM, respectively, unless indicated otherwise. The plate was incubated for 30 minutes at room temperature whereafter NanoGlo furimazine (Promega) was added with a final dilution factor of 1000 - 2100. Luminescence spectra (corrected for wavelength-dependent detector sensitivity differences, Tecan internal calibration) were recorded in a plate reader (Tecan Spark 10M) between wavelengths 398 nm and 653 nm with a step size of 15 nm, a bandwidth of 25 nm and an integration time of 100 – 300 ms. Green-over-blue and red-over-blue ratios were calculated by dividing luminescence intensity at 533 ± 12.5 nm (green) or 653 ± 12.5 nm (red) by the intensity at 458 ± 12.5 nm (blue).

Single-target RPA-LUNAS assays. For single-target RPA-LUNAS assays, LUNAS-LB and LUNAS-SB proteins were incubated with 2 – 3x molar excess of gRNA for 15 minutes at 37 °C in LUNAS RNP buffer (20 mM Tris-Cl pH 7.5, 150 mM KCl, 5 mM MgCl₂, 5% (v/v) glycerol, 1 mM DTT, 1 mg/mL BSA) to form RNP complexes. Then, RPA-LUNAS reactions were prepared on ice by first making a master mix containing primers, NanoGlo substrate (Promega), magnesium acetate, TwistAmp rehydration buffer (TwistAmp Basic kit, TwistDx), and LUNAS mix (LUNAS-SB;gRNA A, LUNAS-LB;gRNA B). The lyophilized RPA reaction components (TwistAmp Basic kit, TwistDx) were resuspended with this master mix at 47.5 μL per pellet. Input DNA was prepared by serial dilution in nuclease free water, of which 1 μL was added to a 19 μL RPA reaction in a 96-well white PCR plate (VWR). Final reaction component concentrations included: 480 – 500 nM primers (each), 1000x diluted NanoGlo substrate, 14 mM magnesium acetate, 59% (v/v) TwistAmp rehydration buffer, 1 nM LUNAS-LB RNP and 10 nM LUNAS-SB RNP (added to the reaction master mix as a 5 – 10x LUNAS sensor mix in LUNAS RNP buffer). Luminescence intensities (corrected for wavelength-dependent detector sensitivity differences, Tecan internal calibration) were measured for 1 hour at wavelengths 458, 533 and 653 nm (bandwidth ± 12.5) with an integration time of 100 – 300 ms at 40 °C in a pre-heated aluminum plateholder in a Tecan Spark 10 M plate reader.

Multiplex RPA-LUNAS assays. For one-pot multiplex RPA-LUNAS assays, reactions were prepared in the same manner as for single target RPA-LUNAS reactions, now including additional primers (480 – 500 nM each, unless indicated otherwise), LUNAS sensor components and a calibrator luciferase at indicated concentrations. The additional LUNAS RNPs and a calibrator were included in the 5 – 10x LUNAS sensor mix added to the reaction master mix for resuspending RPA reaction pellets (47.5 μL per pellet). Green-over-blue and red-over-blue ratios were calculated by dividing luminescence intensity at 533 ± 12.5 nm (green) or 653 ± 12.5 nm (red) by the intensity at 458 ± 12.5 nm (blue). Spectral bleed-through correction was performed by subtracting a fraction (empirically determined correction factor) of the luminescence intensity at peak wavelength from the level at the secondary color channel.

T7 phage, SARS-CoV-2, HsRPP30 and CT/NG assay design and synthetic target nucleic acids. The T7 phage and SARS-CoV-2 assays used in this study were the same as previously described²¹. The human Ribonuclease P protein subunit p30 assay was designed as a control for proper sample preparation including stabilization of RNA, by specifically detecting only the mRNA transcript (transcript variant 2, Genbank NM_006413.5) through its cDNA^{38,46}. This was achieved by designing gRNAs binding to exons 7 and 9, with a suitable LUNAS interspace of 40 bp in the cDNA, but an unbridgeable 998 bp interspace in the gene. Also at the level of the RPA reaction the discrimination between cDNA and genomic DNA is made, with one primer binding at the exon 7 and one primer binding at the interface of exon 9 and 10. Target cDNA fragment was obtained by performing a PCR reaction

(NEB Phusion) on a cDNA plasmid obtained from GenScript (OHu31762D, RPP30(NM_006413.4) ORF Clone) (see sequence in SI).

For *C. trachomatis*, the *uvrC* gene is targeted, as described by Brunelle et al. as a region on the genome that is highly conserved between subtypes⁴⁷. For the gonorrhoea assay, the *dcmH* gene is targeted and screened for conserved regions between subtypes of the bacteria. An alignment of a set of publicly available DNA sequences of this gene (GenBank: NZ CP098462, NZ CP078116, NZ CP048929, NZ CP078113, NZ CP097846) was analyzed and conserved regions were used as a target in the assay. gRNAs were designed as described by van der Veer et al.²¹. Synthetic crRNA and tracrRNA (IDT) were combined 1:1 in IDT nuclease free duplex buffer (30 mM HEPES, pH 7.5; 100 mM potassium acetate) to 4 μ M final gRNA duplex concentration, followed by heating at 95°C for 5 minutes and subsequent gradually cooling to room temperature, generating gRNA. Aliquots of gRNA were stored at -30°C. RPA primers were designed following TwistAmp (TwistDx) primer design guidelines aiming at small amplicons. Target PCR amplicons were obtained by performing a PCR reaction (NEB Phusion) on DNA extracted from patient samples (CT) or from a clinical strain (NG) (see sequence in SI). The PCR reactions were repeated for a second time to dilute the concentration of chromosomal DNA, for accurately quantifying fragment concentration through NanoDrop A₂₆₀ measurement. All gRNA, primers and PCR amplicon sequences can be found in the supplementary information.

CT/NG clinical validation. Urine or swab specimens were transferred to Cobas® PCR medium and subsequent DNA isolates were obtained using the Magpure96 system (Roche). Samples were diluted 2x with nuclease free water prior to use in qPCR or LUNAS assays. Routine qPCR tests for CT and NG were performed using the commercial Presto 100 CT/NG PCR Kit (Goffin Molecular Diagnostics) and the CFX96 real-time PCR system (Bio-Rad), according to manufacturer's instructions. Additional qPCR testing to confirm double-positives was performed using an in-house qPCR assay targeting the NG TFPP-gene. The plate reader assays were performed similar to the multiplex RPA-LUNAS on synthetic targets, combining 1 μ L DNA isolate with 19 μ L of RPA-LUNAS reaction. The preparation of the camera-based assays was also similar to the multiplex RPA-LUNAS on synthetic targets, but with increased calibrator concentration (625 pM) and combining 1 μ L DNA isolate with 24 μ L of RPA-LUNAS reaction. Reactions were placed in a heating block set to 40 °C in a 3D-printed light-tight black box. Luminescence was recorded using a Sony DSC-RX100 III digital camera fitted through a hole of in the lid of the black box, with 120s exposure time, f/1.8 and ISO-6400. The camera was controlled using wireless control remote (Pixel, TW-283) for continuous shooting over 1 hour. RAW files were converted to JPG files using Adobe Camera Raw / Photoshop, and mean blue (B), green (G) and red (R) intensities per well were extracted from split RGB channels using a custom MATLAB (Mathworks) script (see SI). Reactions were regarded as positive for CT if the blue/red ratio (BR) exceeded a threshold value defined as $BR_{\text{threshold}}(t_i) = BR_{\text{smoothNTC}}(t_i) + 8 \cdot SD_{\text{all}}(t=5 \text{ min})$, with $BR_{\text{smoothNTC}}(t_i)$ the moving average blue/red ratio of the NTC over (t_{i-2}, t_{i+2}) , and $SD_{\text{all}}(t=5 \text{ min})$ the standard deviation of the blue/red ratio of all reactions at $t = 5 \text{ min}$. Reactions were regarded as positive for NG if the green/red ratio (GR) exceeded a threshold value defined as $GR_{\text{threshold}}(t_i) = GR_{\text{smoothNTC}}(t_i) + 16 \cdot SD_{\text{all}}(t=5 \text{ min})$, with $GR_{\text{smoothNTC}}(t_i)$ the moving average green/red ratio of the NTC over (t_{i-2}, t_{i+2}) , and $SD_{\text{all}}(t=5 \text{ min})$ the standard deviation of the green/red ratio of all reactions at $t = 5 \text{ min}$. The reported LUNAS threshold time equals the first t satisfying the condition $BR(t) > BR_{\text{threshold}}(t)$ and/or $GR(t) > GR_{\text{threshold}}(t)$.

Digital droplet PCR (ddPCR) to determine target loads. To quantify absolute uvrC gene (CT) and dcmH gene (NG) target concentrations and correlate these with Presto 100 CT/NG PCR Ct values, Droplet Digital PCR (ddPCR) was performed for 16 DNA isolates (5 CT positive, 5 NG positive, 6 double-positive) using in-house ddPCR assays targeting the omcB gene (CT) (Last et al., 2014⁴⁸) and the TFPP gene (NG, Supplementary table S4) using the QX200 ddPCR system (Bio-Rad). Targets for LUNAS (uvrC, dcmH) and ddPCR (omcB, TFPP) are all single-copy genomic targets and are therefore a proxy of the pathogen load (the actual load may be lower due to DNA remnants of dead bacteria potentially being detected as well). Samples were diluted 1-100 fold to avoid overloading and 10 µL of diluted sample was added per 22 µL ddPCR reaction. 20 µL of this reaction was used for droplet generation. Data was analyzed with QX Manager 1.2 Standard Edition software (Bio-Rad).

Safety statement

No unexpected or unusually high safety hazards were encountered.

Ethics statement

The samples used here were obtained as part of standard STI testing and patients did not object to the use of remnant sample material for quality purposes and research. Approval of local medical ethics review committee was not required as samples (DNA isolates) did not contain patient information and were used for an application in line with the reason for sample obtainment.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is freely available and includes: gRNA, primer, target DNA and protein coding sequences, and supplementary figures and tables showing further details of the reported work.

Data and Material Availability

All data underlying the presented figures and findings are available upon reasonable request to the corresponding author (m.merkx@tue.nl).

Plasmids for recombinant expression of SpdCas9-mNG-LB, SpdCas9-SB-mNG, SpdCas9*-SB_K-4C, SpdCas9*-LB_T41C, NL*_T41C and NB_T41C will be made available through AddGene after publication.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Author Contributions

H.v.d.V. and Y.d.S. both conceived and designed the study, performed experiments, analyzed the data, and wrote the manuscript. J.C., I.K., B.T., B.G., H.V. and M.B. contributed to the design of LUNAS and calibrator color variants and initial experiments. J.C. and I.K. designed initial duplex RPA-LUNAS assays and performed related experiments. J.S. and J.M. provided qPCR / ddPCR data. P.W. provided clinical NG and CT samples. A.L. and J.S. supervised qPCR and ddPCR experiments and provided important

feedback. M.M. conceived, designed, and supervised the study, analyzed the data, and wrote the manuscript. All authors discussed the results and commented on the manuscript.

Notes

H.v.d.V. and M.M. co-founded social enterprise Spotlight Dx B.V. to further develop, manufacture and deploy the LUNAS technology for infectious disease diagnosis in low-resource regions. The company is steward-owned and H.v.d.V. and M.M. have limited financial interest. The other authors declare no competing financial interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to thank Eva van Aalen for co-supervising early experiments. We would like to thank Mayk Lucchesi (MUMC Maastricht) for preparing clinical samples. This work was supported by the Dutch research council | Nationaal Regieorgaan Praktijkgericht Onderzoek SIA (RAAK.PRO04.063) and the Eindhoven University Fund (COVID-19 Engineering Fund).

References

- (1) Li, J.; Macdonald, J.; Von Stetten, F. Review: A Comprehensive Summary of a Decade Development of the Recombinase Polymerase Amplification. *The Analyst* **2019**, *144* (1), 31–67. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8AN01621F>.
- (2) Becherer, L.; Borst, N.; Bakheit, M.; Frischmann, S.; Zengerle, R.; Von Stetten, F. Loop-Mediated Isothermal Amplification (LAMP) – Review and Classification of Methods for Sequence-Specific Detection. *Anal. Methods* **2020**, *12* (6), 717–746. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9AY02246E>.
- (3) Glökler, J.; Lim, T. S.; Ida, J.; Frohme, M. Isothermal Amplifications – a Comprehensive Review on Current Methods. *Crit. Rev. Biochem. Mol. Biol.* **2021**, *56* (6), 543–586. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10409238.2021.1937927>.
- (4) De Stigter, Y.; Van Der Veer, H. J.; Rosier, B. J. H. M.; Merckx, M. Bioluminescent Intercalating Dyes for Ratiometric Nucleic Acid Detection. *ACS Chem. Biol.* **2024**, *19* (2), 575–583. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscchembio.3c00755>.
- (5) Gootenberg, J. S.; Abudayyeh, O. O.; Lee, J. W.; Essletzbichler, P.; Dy, A. J.; Joung, J.; Verdine, V.; Donghia, N.; Daringer, N. M.; Freije, C. A.; Myhrvold, C.; Bhattacharyya, R. P.; Livny, J.; Regev, A.; Koonin, E. V.; Hung, D. T.; Sabeti, P. C.; Collins, J. J.; Zhang, F. Nucleic Acid Detection with CRISPR-Cas13a/C2c2. *Science* **2017**, *356* (6336), 438–442. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aam9321>.
- (6) Chen, J. S.; Ma, E.; Harrington, L. B.; Da Costa, M.; Tian, X.; Palefsky, J. M.; Doudna, J. A. CRISPR-Cas12a Target Binding Unleashes Indiscriminate Single-Stranded DNase Activity. *Science* **2018**, *360* (6387), 436–439. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aar6245>.
- (7) Li, S.-Y.; Cheng, Q.-X.; Wang, J.-M.; Li, X.-Y.; Zhang, Z.-L.; Gao, S.; Cao, R.-B.; Zhao, G.-P.; Wang, J. CRISPR-Cas12a-Assisted Nucleic Acid Detection. *Cell Discov.* **2018**, *4* (1), 20. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41421-018-0028-z>.
- (8) Kaminski, M. M.; Abudayyeh, O. O.; Gootenberg, J. S.; Zhang, F.; Collins, J. J. CRISPR-Based Diagnostics. *Nat. Biomed. Eng.* **2021**, *5* (7), 643–656. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41551-021-00760-7>.
- (9) Myhrvold, C.; Freije, C. A.; Gootenberg, J. S.; Abudayyeh, O. O.; Metsky, H. C.; Durbin, A. F.; Kellner, M. J.; Tan, A. L.; Paul, L. M.; Parham, L. A.; Garcia, K. F.; Barnes, K. G.; Chak, B.; Mondini, A.; Nogueira, M. L.; Isern, S.; Michael, S. F.; Lorenzana, I.; Yozwiak, N. L.; MacInnis, B. L.; Bosch, I.; Gehrke, L.; Zhang, F.; Sabeti, P. C. Field-Deployable Viral Diagnostics Using CRISPR-Cas13. *Science* **2018**, *360* (6387), 444–448. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aas8836>.
- (10) Lewinski, M. A.; Alby, K.; Babady, N. E.; Butler-Wu, S. M.; Bard, J. D.; Greninger, A. L.; Hanson, K.; Naccache, S. N.; Newton, D.; Temple-Smolkin, R. L.; Nolte, F. Exploring the Utility of Multiplex Infectious Disease Panel Testing for Diagnosis of Infection in Different Body Sites. *J. Mol. Diagn.* **2023**, *25* (12), 857–875. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmoldx.2023.08.005>.
- (11) Schmitz, J. E.; Stratton, C. W.; Persing, D. H.; Tang, Y.-W. Forty Years of Molecular Diagnostics for Infectious Diseases. *J. Clin. Microbiol.* **2022**, *60* (10), e02446-21. <https://doi.org/10.1128/jcm.02446-21>.
- (12) Ackerman, C. M.; Myhrvold, C.; Thakku, S. G.; Freije, C. A.; Metsky, H. C.; Yang, D. K.; Ye, S. H.; Boehm, C. K.; Kosoko-Thoroddsen, T.-S. F.; Kehe, J.; Nguyen, T. G.; Carter, A.; Kulesa, A.; Barnes, J. R.; Dugan, V. G.; Hung, D. T.; Blainey, P. C.; Sabeti, P. C. Massively Multiplexed Nucleic Acid Detection with Cas13. *Nature* **2020**, *582* (7811), 277–282. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2279-8>.
- (13) Welch, N. L.; Zhu, M.; Hua, C.; Weller, J.; Mirhashemi, M. E.; Nguyen, T. G.; Mantena, S.; Bauer, M. R.; Shaw, B. M.; Ackerman, C. M.; Thakku, S. G.; Tse, M. W.; Kehe, J.; Uwera, M.-M.; Eversley, J. S.; Bielwaski, D. A.; McGrath, G.; Braidt, J.; Johnson, J.; Cerrato, F.; Moreno, G. K.; Krasilnikova, L. A.; Petros, B. A.; Gionet, G. L.; King, E.; Huard, R. C.; Jalbert, S. K.; Cleary, M. L.; Fitzgerald, N. A.; Gabriel, S. B.; Gallagher, G. R.; Smole, S. C.; Madoff, L. C.; Brown, C. M.; Keller, M. W.; Wilson, M.

- M.; Kirby, M. K.; Barnes, J. R.; Park, D. J.; Siddle, K. J.; Happi, C. T.; Hung, D. T.; Springer, M.; MacInnis, B. L.; Lemieux, J. E.; Rosenberg, E.; Branda, J. A.; Blainey, P. C.; Sabeti, P. C.; Myhrvold, C. Multiplexed CRISPR-Based Microfluidic Platform for Clinical Testing of Respiratory Viruses and Identification of SARS-CoV-2 Variants. *Nat. Med.* **2022**, *28* (5), 1083–1094. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-022-01734-1>.
- (14) Xu, Z.; Chen, D.; Li, T.; Yan, J.; Zhu, J.; He, T.; Hu, R.; Li, Y.; Yang, Y.; Liu, M. Microfluidic Space Coding for Multiplexed Nucleic Acid Detection via CRISPR-Cas12a and Recombinase Polymerase Amplification. *Nat. Commun.* **2022**, *13* (1), 6480. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-34086-y>.
- (15) Oh, S. J.; Park, B. H.; Jung, J. H.; Choi, G.; Lee, D. C.; Kim, D. H.; Seo, T. S. Centrifugal Loop-Mediated Isothermal Amplification Microdevice for Rapid, Multiplex and Colorimetric Foodborne Pathogen Detection. *Biosens. Bioelectron.* **2016**, *75*, 293–300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2015.08.052>.
- (16) Yin, J.; Zou, Z.; Hu, Z.; Zhang, S.; Zhang, F.; Wang, B.; Lv, S.; Mu, Y. A “Sample-in-Multiplex-Digital-Answer-out” Chip for Fast Detection of Pathogens. *Lab. Chip* **2020**, *20* (5), 979–986. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9LC01143A>.
- (17) Gootenberg, J. S.; Abudayyeh, O. O.; Kellner, M. J.; Joung, J.; Collins, J. J.; Zhang, F. Multiplexed and Portable Nucleic Acid Detection Platform with Cas13, Cas12a, and Csm6. *Science* **2018**, *360* (6387), 439–444. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aag0179>.
- (18) Greensmith, R.; Lape, I. T.; Riella, C. V.; Schubert, A. J.; Metzger, J. J.; Dighe, A. S.; Tan, X.; Hemmer, B.; Rau, J.; Wendlinger, S.; Diederich, N.; Schütz, A.; Riella, L. V.; Kaminski, M. M. CRISPR-Enabled Point-of-Care Genotyping for APOL1 Genetic Risk Assessment. *EMBO Mol. Med.* **2024**, *16* (10), 2619–2637. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44321-024-00126-x>.
- (19) Arizti-Sanz, J.; Bradley, A.; Zhang, Y. B.; Boehm, C. K.; Freije, C. A.; Grunberg, M. E.; Kosoko-Thoroddsen, T.-S. F.; Welch, N. L.; Pillai, P. P.; Mantena, S.; Kim, G.; Uwanibe, J. N.; John, O. G.; Eromon, P. E.; Kocher, G.; Gross, R.; Lee, J. S.; Hensley, L. E.; MacInnis, B. L.; Johnson, J.; Springer, M.; Happi, C. T.; Sabeti, P. C.; Myhrvold, C. Simplified Cas13-Based Assays for the Fast Identification of SARS-CoV-2 and Its Variants. *Nat. Biomed. Eng.* **2022**, *6* (8), 932–943. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41551-022-00889-z>.
- (20) Zhang, Y. B.; Arizti-Sanz, J.; Bradley, A.; Huang, Y.; Kosoko-Thoroddsen, T.-S. F.; Sabeti, P. C.; Myhrvold, C. CRISPR-Based Assays for Point-of-Need Detection and Subtyping of Influenza. *J. Mol. Diagn.* **2024**, *26* (7), 599–612. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmoldx.2024.04.004>.
- (21) van der Veer, H. J.; van Aalen, E. A.; Michielsen, C. M. S.; Hanckmann, E. T. L.; Deckers, J.; van Borren, M. M. G. J.; Flipse, J.; Loonen, A. J. M.; Schoeber, J. P. H.; Merckx, M. Glow-in-the-Dark Infectious Disease Diagnostics Using CRISPR-Cas9-Based Split Luciferase Complementation. *ACS Cent. Sci.* **2023**, *9* (4), 657–667. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscentsci.2c01467>.
- (22) Suzuki, K.; Kimura, T.; Shinoda, H.; Bai, G.; Daniels, M. J.; Arai, Y.; Nakano, M.; Nagai, T. Five Colour Variants of Bright Luminescent Protein for Real-Time Multicolour Bioimaging. *Nat. Commun.* **2016**, *7* (1), 13718. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms13718>.
- (23) Ni, Y.; Rosier, B. J. H. M.; van Aalen, E. A.; Hanckmann, E. T. L.; Biewenga, L.; Pistikou, A.-M. M.; Timmermans, B.; Vu, C.; Roos, S.; Arts, R.; Li, W.; de Greef, T. F. A.; van Borren, M. M. G. J.; van Kuppeveld, F. J. M.; Bosch, B.-J.; Merckx, M. A Plug-and-Play Platform of Ratiometric Bioluminescent Sensors for Homogeneous Immunoassays. *Nat. Commun.* **2021**, *12* (1), 4586. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-24874-3>.
- (24) Van Aalen, E. A.; Wouters, S. F. A.; Verzijl, D.; Merckx, M. Bioluminescent RAPPID Sensors for the Single-Step Detection of Soluble Axl and Multiplex Analysis of Cell Surface Cancer Biomarkers. *Anal. Chem.* **2022**, *94* (17), 6548–6556. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.2c00297>.
- (25) Chu, J.; Oh, Y.; Sens, A.; Ataie, N.; Dana, H.; Macklin, J. J.; Laviv, T.; Welf, E. S.; Dean, K. M.; Zhang, F.; Kim, B. B.; Tang, C. T.; Hu, M.; Baird, M. A.; Davidson, M. W.; Kay, M. A.; Fiolka, R.; Yasuda, R.; Kim, D. S.; Ng, H.-L.; Lin, M. Z. A Bright Cyan-Excitable Orange Fluorescent Protein Facilitates

- Dual-Emission Microscopy and Enhances Bioluminescence Imaging in Vivo. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **2016**, *34* (7).
- (26) Tian, X.; Zhang, Y.; Li, X.; Xiong, Y.; Wu, T.; Ai, H.-W. A Luciferase Prosubstrate and a Red Bioluminescent Calcium Indicator for Imaging Neuronal Activity in Mice. *Nat. Commun.* **2022**, *13* (1), 3967. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-31673-x>.
- (27) Hiblot, J.; Yu, Q.; Sabbadini, M. D. B.; Reymond, L.; Xue, L.; Schena, A.; Sallin, O.; Hill, N.; Griss, R.; Johnsson, K. Luciferases with Tunable Emission Wavelengths. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2017**, *56* (46), 14556–14560. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201708277>.
- (28) Machleidt, T.; Woodroffe, C. C.; Schwinn, M. K.; Méndez, J.; Robers, M. B.; Zimmerman, K.; Otto, P.; Daniels, D. L.; Kirkland, T. A.; Wood, K. V. NanoBRET—A Novel BRET Platform for the Analysis of Protein–Protein Interactions. *ACS Chem. Biol.* **2015**, *10* (8), 1797–1804. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscchembio.5b00143>.
- (29) Thirukkumaran, O. M.; Wang, C.; Asouzu, N. J.; Fron, E.; Rocha, S.; Hofkens, J.; Lavis, L. D.; Mizuno, H. Improved HaloTag Ligand Enables BRET Imaging With NanoLuc. *Front. Chem.* **2019**, *7*, 938. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fchem.2019.00938>.
- (30) Russo, F.; Civili, B.; Winssinger, N. Bright Red Bioluminescence from Semisynthetic NanoLuc (sNLuc). *ACS Chem. Biol.* **2024**, *19* (5), 1035–1039. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscchembio.4c00033>.
- (31) Sednev, M. V.; Belov, V. N.; Hell, S. W. Fluorescent Dyes with Large Stokes Shifts for Super-Resolution Optical Microscopy of Biological Objects: A Review. *Methods Appl. Fluoresc.* **2015**, *3* (4), 042004. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2050-6120/3/4/042004>.
- (32) Vollmer, F.; Rettig, W.; Birckner, E. Photochemical Mechanisms Producing Large Fluorescence Stokes Shifts. *J. Fluoresc.* **1994**, *4* (1), 65–69. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01876657>.
- (33) Piatkevich, K. D.; Malashkevich, V. N.; Almo, S. C.; Verkhusha, V. V. Engineering ESPT Pathways Based on Structural Analysis of LSSmKate Red Fluorescent Proteins with Large Stokes Shift. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2010**, *132* (31), 10762–10770. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja101974k>.
- (34) Engelen, W.; van de Wiel, K. M.; Meijer, L. H. H.; Saha, B.; Merckx, M. Nucleic Acid Detection Using BRET-Beacons Based on Bioluminescent Protein-DNA Hybrids. *Chem. Commun. Camb. Engl.* **2017**, *53* (19), 2862–2865. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c6cc10032e>.
- (35) Van Aalen, E. A.; De Vries, I. R.; Hanckmann, E. T. L.; Stevens, J. R. F.; Romagnoli, T. R.; Derijks, L. J. J.; Broeren, M. A. C.; Merckx, M. Point-of-Care Therapeutic Drug Monitoring of Tumour Necrosis Factor- α Inhibitors Using a Single Step Immunoassay. *Sens. Diagn.* **2023**, *2* (6), 1492–1500. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3SD00131H>.
- (36) Sternberg, S. H.; LaFrance, B.; Kaplan, M.; Doudna, J. A. Conformational Control of DNA Target Cleavage by CRISPR–Cas9. *Nature* **2015**, *527* (7576), 110–113. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature15544>.
- (37) Yan, Y.; Chang, L.; Wang, L. Laboratory Testing of SARS-CoV, MERS-CoV, and SARS-CoV-2 (2019-nCoV): Current Status, Challenges, and Countermeasures. *Rev. Med. Virol.* **2020**, *30* (3), e2106. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rmv.2106>.
- (38) Rosebrock, A. P. DNA Cross-Reactivity of the CDC-Specified SARS-CoV-2 Specimen Control Leads to Potential for False Negatives and Underreporting of Viral Infection. *Clin. Chem.* **2021**, *67* (2), 435–437. <https://doi.org/10.1093/clinchem/hvaa284>.
- (39) Wi, T. E.; Ndowa, F. J.; Ferreyra, C.; Kelly-Cirino, C.; Taylor, M. M.; Toskin, I.; Kiarie, J.; Santesso, N.; Unemo, M. Diagnosing Sexually Transmitted Infections in Resource-constrained Settings: Challenges and Ways Forward. *J. Int. AIDS Soc.* **2019**, *22* (S6), e25343. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jia2.25343>.
- (40) *Global Progress Report on HIV, Viral Hepatitis and Sexually Transmitted Infections, 2021. Accountability for the Global Health Sector Strategies 2016-2021: Actions for Impact*, 1st ed.; World Health Organization: Geneva, 2021.

- (41) Sati, H.; Carrara, E.; Savoldi, A.; Hansen, P.; Garlasco, J.; Campagnaro, E.; Boccia, S.; Castillo-Polo, J. A.; Magrini, E.; Garcia-Vello, P.; Wool, E.; Gigante, V.; Duffy, E.; Cassini, A.; Huttner, B.; Pardo, P. R.; Naghavi, M.; Mirzayev, F.; Zignol, M.; Cameron, A.; Tacconelli, E.; Aboderin, A.; Al Ghoribi, M.; Al-Salman, J.; Amir, A.; Apisarnthanarak, A.; Blaser, M.; El-Sharif, A.; Essack, S.; Harbarth, S.; Huang, X.; Kapoor, G.; Knight, G.; Muhwa, J. C.; Monnet, D. L.; Ousassa, T.; Sacaquique, R.; Severin, J.; Sugai, M.; Taneja, N.; Umubyeyi Nyaruhirira, A. The WHO Bacterial Priority Pathogens List 2024: A Prioritisation Study to Guide Research, Development, and Public Health Strategies against Antimicrobial Resistance. *Lancet Infect. Dis.* **2025**, S1473309925001185. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(25\)00118-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(25)00118-5).
- (42) Fuchs, R. T.; Curcuru, J.; Mabuchi, M.; Yourik, P.; Robb, G. B. Cas12a Trans-Cleavage Can Be Modulated in Vitro and Is Active on ssDNA, dsDNA, and RNA. *Molecular Biology* April 8, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1101/600890>.
- (43) Luo, H.; Zeng, L.; Yin, X.; Pan, Y.; Yang, J.; Liu, M.; Qin, X.; Feng, Z.; Chen, W.; Zheng, H. An Isothermal CRISPR-Based Diagnostic Assay for *Neisseria Gonorrhoeae* and *Chlamydia Trachomatis* Detection. *Microbiol. Spectr.* **2023**, 11 (6), e00464-23. <https://doi.org/10.1128/spectrum.00464-23>.
- (44) Wouters, S. F. A.; Vugs, W. J. P.; Arts, R.; De Leeuw, N. M.; Teeuwen, R. W. H.; Merckx, M. Bioluminescent Antibodies through Photoconjugation of Protein G–Luciferase Fusion Proteins. *Bioconjug. Chem.* **2020**, 31 (3), 656–662. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.bioconjchem.9b00804>.
- (45) *Point-of-Care Tests for Sexually Transmitted Infections: Target Product Profiles*; World Health Organization: Geneva, 2023.
- (46) Dekker, R. J.; Ensink, W. A.; Van Leeuwen, S.; Rauwerda, H.; Breit, T. M. Overhauling a Faulty Control in the CDC-Recommended SARS-CoV-2 RT-PCR Test Panel. June 13, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.06.12.147819>.
- (47) Brunelle, B. W.; Sensabaugh, G. F. The *ompA* Gene in *Chlamydia Trachomatis* Differs in Phylogeny and Rate of Evolution from Other Regions of the Genome. *Infect. Immun.* **2006**, 74 (1), 578–585. <https://doi.org/10.1128/IAI.74.1.578-585.2006>.
- (48) Last, A. R.; Roberts, C. H.; Cassama, E.; Nabicassa, M.; Molina-Gonzalez, S.; Burr, S. E.; Mabey, D. C. W.; Bailey, R. L.; Holland, M. J. Plasmid Copy Number and Disease Severity in Naturally Occurring Ocular *Chlamydia Trachomatis* Infection. *J. Clin. Microbiol.* **2014**, 52 (1), 324–327. <https://doi.org/10.1128/JCM.02618-13>.